

Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional: Mapping Research Topics using Library Research and VOSviewer Bibliometrics

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Abstract

This research aims to map research topics around Bank OCBC NISP Syariah and Conventional using a qualitative approach, which is a library research. The data collection technique is: first, open the Perish/Harzing software, then search for journals based on the title words category with the key words " Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional " within the entire year period. Second, collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles. Third, download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) format from all journals for which data has been collected. Fourth, enter the RIS data file into Mendeley software Desktop. Data analysis technique by mapping research topics around Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional based on journals that have been collected. The research results show that There are 6 mapping research topics using literature studies regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Financing/credit products; (4) Savings/credit products; (5) Customer behavior; and (6) Other issues. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the research gaps in this topic.

Keywords: Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional; Library Research; Bibliometrics; VOSviewer

Introduction

The development of the banking system is currently experiencing significant changes, with digitalization in the financial system. This change has a positive impact on customers. Banking has a strategic role in collecting and channeling funds from society to other communities, with the aim of improving the standard of living of many people through savings. Until now, banking has developed rapidly, triggering the growth of the industrial, service and trade sectors in Indonesia (Marwansyah and Yohanas, 2015).

Sharia banking has great potential and has great opportunities for Muslim communities. Currently, there are two types of banking growing in Indonesia, namely conventional banking and sharia banking. The banking operational system in Indonesia is divided into these two types. Conventional banking is banking that carries out its operations using interest as a profit, while sharia banking is banking that carries out its operations in accordance with Islamic economic principles, namely by using the principle of profit sharing. Sharia banking prohibits the use of interest in making profits and also does not charge interest on loans, because interest is usury and is forbidden in Islam (Marimin A, Romadhoni AH, and Tira NF, 2015). Bank OCBC NISP is the fourth oldest banking institution in Indonesia which was founded in Bandung

on April 4 1941. Bank OCBC NISP is a banking institution that is largely owned by the governments of Singapore and Indonesia. Bank OCBC NISP is one of the strongest banks in Asia, especially in terms of services (Luh AM, I Gst Agung KGS, 2016).

Scientific publications about Bank OCBC NISP Syariah continue to increase from year to year. This research is important to conduct to determine the development of Bank OCBC NISP. Bank OCBC NISP has 32 published documents via the Garuda website from 2013 to 2022 using the keyword "Bank OCBC NISP". This shows that there is increasing interest in research related to Bank OCBC NISP.

Luh AM & I Gst Agung KGS, (2016) conducted research at Bank OCBC NISP in Denpasar with a sample size of 105 respondents using multiple regression analysis techniques by distributing questionnaires. The results of the analysis from this research found that company image has a very significant influence on customer satisfaction at Bank OCBC NISP in Denpasar. Apart from that, service quality also has a significant influence on Bank OCBC NISP customer satisfaction in Denpasar.

The aim of this research is to map research topics surrounding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional uses library research (library research). The difference between this research and previous research is that this research explains all research topics regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional, so that it can be a reference for other researchers. The implication and contribution of this research is the mapping of research topics surrounding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional, both those that are often or rarely researched by researchers, so that other researchers can find out the research gaps in this topic.

Literature Review

Bank OCBC NISP is a combination of Bank OCBC and Bank OCBC Indonesia. The merger of these two banks strengthens the consumer and commercial financing sector. Bank OCBC Indonesia's advantages in the field of corporate financing also help provide more products and services according to customer needs in various types of customer segmentation. The merger of these two banks resulted in a bank that is strong and highly competitive with other increasingly competent banks (Usmany, LR, & Badjra, I. B, 2019).

Sharia financial inclusion refers to efforts to ensure that all individuals and economic entities, regardless of their economic, social, or geographic background, have fair and appropriate access to financial products and services that comply with sharia principles. Sharia principles are Islamic economic rules and guidelines that prohibit *riba* (interest), excessive speculation, and investment in businesses that are forbidden under Islamic law. Sharia financial inclusion includes a variety of financial products and services, such as savings, microfinance, insurance, investment and other financial instruments, that comply with sharia principles. The aim of sharia financial inclusion is to increase public access to financial services that are in accordance with the values and principles of the Islamic religion. Sharia financial inclusion has a positive impact on the economy, including reducing poverty, improving community welfare, and strengthening financial system stability. Apart from that, sharia financial inclusion also supports the development of the sharia financial sector as a whole, which involves financial institutions such as sharia banks, sharia insurance companies and sharia capital markets.

Library research is a type of research that focuses on the analysis, understanding and synthesis of existing literature in a particular field of knowledge or topic. The aim of Library Research research is to identify the latest developments, weaknesses, strengths, findings and trends in the relevant research field. In contrast to experimental research or field research, Library Research research does not involve collecting primary data through observation, interviews, or experiments. Instead, researchers collect data from secondary sources such as books, scientific journals, articles and other academic documents. After collecting data, researchers then analyze, compare, and organize the literature to achieve a deeper understanding of the topic under study.

Bibliometric studies are a research method used to analyze and measure scientific publications in a particular field, using quantitative data. In bibliometric studies, the data analyzed includes information about the number of publications, authors, subjects, publication sources, citations, and impact factor. The goal of bibliometric studies is to provide an overview of trends and patterns in scientific publications, as well as measure the impact of these publications on the academic community and industry. Bibliometric studies can be used to identify emerging research areas, measure research performance, and compare performance between researchers, institutions, or countries. Bibliometric studies are usually carried out using bibliometric software, such as Web of Science, Scopus, or Google Scholar. Bibliometric methods can also be used to conduct qualitative analysis, such as content analysis or other qualitative analysis, to understand the issues expressed in certain scientific publications (Dubyna et al., 2022).

VOSviewer is open source software used in bibliometric studies to visualize and analyze the network of links between documents or scientific publications. VOSviewer can be used to analyze bibliometric data collected from various sources, such as Scopus, Web of Science, or Google Scholar. VOSviewer can be used to perform quantitative and qualitative analysis, such as cluster identification, citation analysis, and topic mapping. In cluster analysis, VOSviewer can group scientific publications into similar groups based on their association with a particular topic. Citation analysis can be used to identify the most cited scientific publications in a research field. Topic mapping can be used to identify the most widely discussed research topics in a field. One of the advantages of VOSviewer is its ability to produce attractive and easy-to-understand visualizations, such as heatmaps, network graphs and topic trees. This visualization can help researchers understand patterns and trends in bibliometric data more easily and quickly. VOSviewer can be used by researchers, academics, and practitioners in various research fields, including social science, information science, health, and information technology (van Eck NJ, 2022).

Methodology

This research uses research methods with a mix-method approach, namely quantitative methods in bibliometric studies and qualitative methods in library research. The research object is Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional. The type of data used is secondary data. The scope of the data used is scientific publication articles about Bank OCBC NISP originating from national and accredited journals. The source of data collection comes from the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba). Data analysis tools are Microsoft Excel, Mendeley Desktop, VOSviewer, and Perish software.

Data collection techniques include: (1) visiting the Garuda website and Perish software, then search for journal titles based on the title words category with the keyword " Bank OCBC NISP " for the entire year (20-13-2022); (2) collect journal title data in Microsoft Excel, and identify duplicate journal titles; (3) download files in RIS (Research Information Systems) and PDF (Portable Document Format) formats from all journals for which data has been collected; and (4) inserting the RIS data file into Mendeley Desktop software.

Data analysis techniques include: (1) mapping RIS data files on Mendeley Desktop based on year, author and publisher; (2) mapping the results of bibliometric network visualization and scientific publication trends using the VOSviewer (Visualization of Similarities) algorithm software based on the number of clusters and items; and (3) mapping topics, methods, research findings and research space based on library research (Budianto, 2022) .

Results and Discussion

Mapping the Distribution of Scientific Publications Regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional

Search results for scientific articles published about Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional from 2013 to 2022 show fluctuating changes or ups and downs every year. A total of 6 articles were found in 2016, 2018 and 2019. The collection of journals found consisted of 31 article titles accredited by national journals.

Table 1. Journal article data about Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional by year

Year of Publication	Number of Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Articles	Year of Publication	Number of Articles
2013	2	2017	2	2020	3
2015	3	2018	6	2021	1
2016	6	2019	6	2022	1
Total 31					

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

In table 2, there are 4 affiliates/institutions that appear most frequently in article publications regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional. The Ekobis Dewantara Journal is the journal publishing institution that has published the most research results regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional, namely 3 articles.

Table 2. Institutions and journals that publish scientific publications regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional

Name of Affiliate/Institution	Number of Publications
DEWANTARA ECOBIC JOURNAL	3
Management E-Journal	2
EMBA Journal: Journal of Economic, Management, Business and Accounting Research	2
STIE SULTAN AGUNG MAKER MANAGEMENT JOURNAL	2

ADLIYA: Journal of Law and Humanity, AT-TAWASSUTH: Journal of Islamic Economics, Diponegoro Journal of Management, Jhss (Journal of Humanities and Social Studies), Journal of Business Administration, Bareleng Accounting Journal, Journal of Business and Management Applications (JABM), Scientific Periodical Journal Efficiency, Ecodemica Journal: Journal of Economics, Management and Business, Journal of Effective Economics, Ubhara Management Scientific Journal, Krisnadwipayana Business Management Journal, Jayakarta Management and Business Journal, Competitive Marketing Journal, SeMaRaK JURNAL, Tepak Business Management Journal, Kertha Semaya : Science Journal Law, Collection of Law Faculty Student Journals, Financial Balance: Scientific Journal of Accounting and Finance, Prologia, SKANIKA, TEKUN: Journal of Accounting and Business Studies

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Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Table 3 shows that of the total of 31 research publication articles regarding Bank OCBC NISP Syariah and Conventional on the Garuda website (Digital Referral Garba), the most productive researchers are Murti and Andreas from Pakuan University, with each writing 2 articles.

Table 3. Productivity of researchers around Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional indexed in Garuda (Digital Reference Garba)

Researcher	Number of Publications
Murti, Andreas (PAKUAN UNIVERSITY)	2
Amini, Mochammad Jordie; Safrina (Budi Luhur University), Amri, Mirza Astia (North Sumatra State Islamic University), Nani, Nani Astutik, Endang Puji Rozi, Fahrur (Pamulang University), Badjra, Lisa Rachel Usmany; Ida Bagus (Udayana University), Bunga, M Zakie Hanifan; Berliane Rangga (Ibn Khaldun University Bogor), Chrisyaniardi, Risza (BSI University), efendi, Marisi Butarbutar; Darwin Lie; Erni Juwiling; Efendi (Sultan Agung College of Economics), Harahap, Syahril Effendi; Baru (Putera Batam University), Hidayati, Dita Nur Ikhsana (graduatewiyata Tamansiswa University), Junaidi, Harry Kertaraardja; Ahmad (Tarumanagara University), Lestari, Yunia (Tamansiswa Bachelorwiyata University), Mandey Victor PK; Tangka, Johannes., Silvya.; Lengkong (Sam Ratulangi University), Nariah, Nariah (Pamulang University), Oemar, Yohanas (Riau University), Pradopo, Loeky Rono (Jayakarta College of Economics), Purwanti, I Gusti Ayu Puspawati; I Putu Agus Sukyantara; Ni Putu (Udayana University), Pusparani, Ratih (Brawijaya University), Putra Ahyar, Sakra Brahma; Yuniawan (Diponegoro University), Putri, Devinta Kris Amalia (Scholarwiyata Tamansiswa University), Nani, Nani Astutik, Endang Puji Rozi, Fahrur (Pamulang University), Safrianto, Arief Syah (Krisnadwipayana University), Setiadi, Steffie (Parahyangan Catholic University), Sicillia, Mita (Pamulang University), Soehardi, Asep Hardiansyah; Zahara	1

Tussoleha Rony; Soehardi (Bhayangkara University, Greater Jakarta), Atmosphere, Luh Ayu Mulyaningsih; I Gst Agung Ketut Gede (Udayana University), Sugiharjo, Arief Rachman Hakim; Raden Joko (Mercu Buana University), Thressa, Juliana juliana; Darwin Lie; Efendi efendi; Stefi Ingrid (Sultan Agung College of Economics), Tusadiah, Halimah (UIN Sunan Gunung Djati Bandung), Vinda, Warikkie Tiara Intan (Sam Ratulang University), Worang Prisilia Ester; Pangemanan, Sifrid S., Frederik G.; Sundah (Sam Ratulang University)

Source: Processed data, Microsoft Excel 2016.

Bibliometric Mapping of Research on Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional

The results of searching for articles on the Garuda website (Digital Reference Garba) are exported to RIS (Research Information System) format, then input and analyzed using VOSviewer, are as follows:

Figure 1. Depiction of the growth map relationship surrounding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional

Source: Processed Data, software VOSViewer 1.6.18.

co-word map network visualization of research developments regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional divided into 7 clusters and 175 topics, are as follows:

- Cluster 1. The red color consists of 41 topics, namely: data analysis, rcmpo section, bank, bank cimb niaga tbk and, bank ocbc nisp, bank

ocbc nisp, bopo, car, from this research, from ratios, data, with good criteria, price, employees, organizational justice, work, employee performance, ldr, society, average value, people, organization, this research, this research aims, product influence, performance differences, company, positive and significant, product, pt bank ocbc nisp, capital adequacy ratio, roa, roe, square, t statistics, tbk, data analysis techniques, there is an influence, the aim of this research is, for sharia mortgages, intervening variables.

- Cluster 2. The green color consists of 32 topics, namely: competitive advantage, customer, customer satisfaction, Denpasar, employee performance, indirect influence, interest, KCP Bekasi, Likert scale, number, path analysis, positive effect, positive influence, positive prediction, PT Bank OCBC nisp tbk, quality, questionnaire, regression coefficient, respondent, test results, sample, satisfaction, service, significant effect, situational leadership style, strong contribution, survey, technique, value, variable, work environment, work motivation.
- Cluster 3. The dark blue color consists of 29 topics, namely: activity, analytic network process, anp, ocbc bank, better compensation, compensation, compensation system, employee, highest benefit, improvement, key performance indicator, kpi, measurement, ocbc nisp bank, opportunity, order, preparation, priority, priority weight, process, productivity, risk, scope, second priority, top priority, trade operations, trade operations division employee, trade operations employee, vsm.
- Cluster 4. The yellow color consists of 24 topics, namely: acquisition, additional guarantee, bank ocbc nisp Batam branch, belief, case, collateral, company, comparative analysis, creditor, debtor, dispute, employee loyalty, hindrance, intention, issue, job satisfaction, loan, loan agreement, month, object, organizational culture, credit agreement, skmht, term.
- Cluster 5. The purple color consists of 21 topics, namely: analysis, expectation, factor, independent variable, interest cost, interest expense, internal control, lending, loans interest income, multiple linear regression analysis, net income, period, profit, r square, research, study, t test, tcount, third party fund, variable lending, variables accounting system.
- Cluster 6. The light blue color consists of 17 topics, namely: achievement, bank ocbc nisp branch manado, bank ocbc nisp head office, career, impact, informant, level, media relations, pride, public relations, purposive sampling, role, social class, social life, social status, theory, women's career.
- Cluster 7. The orange color consists of 11 topics, namely: bank ocbc nisp tbk Pekanbaru branch, competence, competency, effect, influence, leadership, motivation, performance, person, population, pt bank ocbc nisp tbk Pekanbaru branch.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding the Financial Performance of Bank OCBC NISP

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 6 topics related to the financial performance of Bank OCBC NISP, namely:

1. First, the effect of working capital use on liquidity.
2. Second, the influence of financial reports on financial performance.

3. Third, the influence of credit interest income and interest costs from Third Party Funds/DPK on net profit.
4. Fourth, the influence of capital adequacy ratios, credit continuity and operational costs on the ability to generate profits.
5. Fifth, performance analysis and financial risk management.
6. Sixth, analyze the company's health level using the RGEC method.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank OCBC NISP Employee Performance

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 19 topics related to the performance of Bank OCBC NISP employees, namely:

1. Acquisition.
2. Organizational culture.
3. Work discipline.
4. Situational leadership style.
5. Career (female employees).
6. Organizational justice.
7. Job satisfaction.
8. Competence.
9. Compensation.
10. Work and family conflict.
11. Organizational communication.
12. Work environment.
13. Time management.
14. Merger.
15. Motivation.
16. Plant climate.
17. Work stress.
18. Office space layout.
19. Trade operations.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank OCBC NISP Customer Behavior

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 14 topics related to Bank OCBC NISP customer behavior, namely:

1. Company image.
2. Green products.
3. Green promotions.
4. Green prices.
5. Green places.
6. Price.
7. Credit card.
8. Convenience.
9. Utility.
10. Service quality.
11. Location.
12. Product.
13. Promotion.
14. Risk.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding OCBC NISP Bank Financing/Credit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 4 research topics related to Bank OCBC NISP financing products, namely:

1. First, default on credit debtors.
2. Second, collateral/guarantee in financing.
3. Third, obstacles to dispute resolution.
4. Fourth, the influence of the accounting system and internal control on lending.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Bank OCBC NISP Savings/Deposit Products

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 1 research topic relates to Bank OCBC NISP savings/deposit products, namely: giving voucher prizes in the Mudharabah savings program.

Mapping Research Topics using Library Research regarding Other Issues at Bank OCBC NISP

Library Research study in previous research journals, the researchers found 2 research topics related to issues at Bank OCBC NISP, namely:

1. First, the simple additive weighting method in the decision support system for selecting premier banking managers.
2. Second, public relations communication during Covid-19 in improving media relations.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the discussion above, it can be concluded that there are 6 Mapping Research Topics using literature studies regarding Bank OCBC NISP Sharia and Conventional, namely: (1) Financial performance; (2) Employee performance; (3) Financing/credit products; (4) Savings/credit products; (5) Customer behavior; and (6) Other issues.

References

- Baranuri, M. Y., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Ijarah pada Industri Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038971>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Akad Mudharabah Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *J-EBIS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Bisnis Islam)*, 7(1), 43–68. <https://doi.org/10.32505/j-ebis.v7i1.3895>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2022). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Akad Musyarakah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JESI (Jurnal Ekonomi Syariah Indonesia)*, 12(1), 25–36. [https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12\(1\).25-36](https://doi.org/10.21927/jesi.2022.12(1).25-36)
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Bibliometric And Literature Review Of Financing Risk In Islamic Banking. *JPS (Jurnal Perbankan Syariah)*, 4(1), 79–97. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.46367/jps.v4i1.1031>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RISIKO REPUTASI PADA

- PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Al-Masraf: Jurnal Lembaga Keuangan Dan Perbankan*, 8(1), 94–113. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.15548/al-masraf.v8i1.425>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Risiko Kredit pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BANCO: Jurnal Manajemen Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 5(1), 20–34. <https://doi.org/10.35905/banco.v5i1.4987>
- Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). RESEARCH MAPPING ON CREDIT RISK IN ISLAMIC AND CONVENTIONAL BANKING. *AL-INFAQ: Jurnal Ekonomi Islam*, 14(1), 73–86. <https://doi.org/10.32507/ajei.v14i1.1862>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2022). Research Mapping of Musyarakah Contracts in Islamic Financial Institutions: VOSviewer Bibliometric Study and Literature Review. *Maliki Islamic Economics Journal*, 2(2), 76–94. <https://doi.org/10.18860/miec.v2i2.17199>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Ju'alah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10040276>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Sharf pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research)*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042641>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Biaya Operasional terhadap Pendapatan Operasional (BOPO) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *JAF (Journal of Accounting and Finance)*, 7(1), 34–48. <https://doi.org/10.25124/jaf.v7i1.5995>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Capital Adequacy Ratio (CAR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037417>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Payout Ratio (DPR) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037141>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dividend Per Share (DPS) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Al-Mal: Jurnal Akuntansi Dan Keuangan Islam*, 4(1), 109–126. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.24042/al-mal.v4i01.16760>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Economic Value Added (EVA) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037270>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Financial Value Added (FVA) pada Perbankan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *BJRM (Bongaya Journal of*

- Research in Management*), 6(2), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.37888/bjrm.v6i2>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Net Operating Margin (NOM) pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Ecobankers: Journal of Economy and Banking*, 4(2), 84–94. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8323115>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan penelitian rasio Net Profit Margin (NPM) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037209>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO NON PERFORMING FINANCING (NPF) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038983>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO RETURN ON INVESTMENT (ROI) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Kompetensi (Competence : Journal of Management Studies)*, 17(1), 66–82. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.21107/kompetensi.v17i1.20002>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN RASIO WORKING CAPITAL TURNOVER (WCT) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037081>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar cash ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037415>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037413>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar current ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037359>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar pengaruh variabel mikroekonomi: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037254>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar quick ratio pada perbankan syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038973>
- Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pengaruh Book Value per Share (BVS) pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Islamic Economics and Business Review*, 2(1). <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185250>

- Budianto, E. W. H., Dewi, N. D. T., & Abidin, U. A. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Rasio Dana Pihak Ketiga (DPK) Pada Perbankan Syariah Dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik Vosviewer Dan Literature Review. *Syar'at Iqtishadi: Journal of Islamic Economics, Finance and Banking*, 7(1), 25–44. <https://doi.org/http://dx.doi.org/10.35448/jiec.v7i1.19887>
- Budianto, E. W. H., Saputra, H. M. G. A., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Koperasi Jasa Keuangan Syariah (KJKS): Studi Bibliometrik VOS viewer dan Literature Review. *EL MUDHORIB: Jurnal Kajian Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 3(2), 131–148. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185180>
- Dewi, N. D. T., Ibad, N. N., Pratopo, G., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian Seputar Manajemen Zakat Pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer Dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomika Dan Bisnis Islam*, 6(1), 1–20. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.26740/jekobi.v6n1.p1-20>
- Febrian, J., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). THE EFFECT OF KNOWLEDGE, TRUST, PRODUCTS, SERVICES AND RELIGIOSITY ON INTEREST IN SAVING. *International Conference of Islamic Economics and Business 9th*, 85–96. <http://repository.uin-malang.ac.id/15487/>
- Gozali, M., Saputra, M. A., Dewi, N. D. T., & Budianto, E. W. H. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR VARIABEL DETERMINAN RETURN ON EQUITY (ROE) PADA PERBANKAN SYARIAH: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *IDEI: Jurnal Ekonomi & Bisnis*, 4(1), 34–47. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.38076/ideijeb.v4i1.151>
- Mawardi, M. I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Tabungan Pensiunan Nasional (BTPN) Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049566>
- Putri, S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Bank Bukopin Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10049572>
- Qudratullah, M. Q., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Murabahah pada Lembaga Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038979>
- Rahmawati, L., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar Bank Tabungan Negara (BTN) syariah dan konvensional: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037422>
- Ratnasari, A. D., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan Topik Penelitian Seputar Akad Rahn (Gadai) pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10038977>
- Rofiah, A., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Wadiah pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research) dan Bibliometrik VOSviewer*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042647>

- Rofika, H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). PEMETAAN PENELITIAN SEPUTAR MAYBANK SYARIAH DAN KONVENSIONAL: STUDI BIBLIOMETRIK VOSVIEWER DAN LITERATURE REVIEW. *Jurnal Ekonomi: Journal of Economic*, 14(1), 28–39. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.47007/jeko.v14i01.6463>
- Rohimah, W., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Bank CIMB Niaga Syariah dan Konvensional: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Jurnal Ekonomi Manajemen Perbankan*, Vol 5, No 1 (2023): JEMPER Januari-Juni, 30–40. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8185264>
- Rohmandika, M. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). Pemetaan Penelitian seputar Variabel Determinan Return On Asset pada Perbankan Syariah: Studi Bibliometrik VOSviewer dan Literature Review. *Eco-Iqtishodi: Jurnal Ilmiah Ekonomi Dan Keuangan Syariah*, 5(1), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.32670/ecoiqtishodi.v5i1.3607>
- Shalsabila, I. H., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad kafalah pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037426>
- Sufia, I., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Akad Salam pada Inklusi Keuangan Syariah: Studi Pustaka (Library Research).* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10042345>
- Zahro, T. S., Budianto, E. W. H., & Dewi, N. D. T. (2023). *Pemetaan topik penelitian seputar akad istishna' pada industri keuangan syariah: studi bibliometrik VOSviewer dan literature review.* <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10037428>